

The impacts of digitalization and sustainability on SMEs' innovation capabilities

Aristei, D.

Department of Economics (UNIPG)

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Introduction

Digital and sustainability orientations are gaining increasing attention as they offer important opportunities to improve and expand firms' operations, production efficiency, and performance (Ardito et al., 2021; Montresor and Vezzani, 2023).

Despite the importance of digitalization and sustainability activities, their joint influence on firms' innovation still remains a largely unexplored topic (Ferreira et al., 2019; Ardito, 2023).

In this study, we contribute to the literature by assessing the direct effects of the adoption of digital technologies and environmental/social sustainability practices on SMEs' innovation capabilities and testing for the presence of complementary effects.

Methods

We use data from the Flash Eurobarometer 486 on "SMEs, Start-ups, Scale-ups and Entrepreneurship", on about 12,000 firms in the European Union.

We focus on different types of firms' innovation (i.e., product, process, organizational, marketing, ecological, and social innovation) and use factor analysis to define a digital orientation score (based on the digital technologies adopted) and a sustainability orientation score (based on the environmental and social sustainability actions implemented).

Probit and count data models, extended to account for the endogeneity of digitalization and sustainability, are employed to analyze firms' innovation probability and the number of innovation types.

Results

Our empirical results indicate that both the adoption of digital technologies and the implementation of sustainability actions significantly increase the probability to innovate and the number of innovation types. We also provide evidence of significant complementarity between digitalization and sustainability in fostering innovation performance.

Furthermore, we find that the impacts of digital and sustainability orientations on innovation are characterized by significant heterogeneity across firm size and are stronger for micro and small-sized enterprises.

These findings call for actions aimed at promoting digitalization and sustainability at the firm level, as they jointly contribute to boost firms' innovation capabilities.

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